

Beyond Rice: The New Dynamics of Food, Fuel, and Farming in India

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ABSTRACT

India's agricultural landscape is undergoing a significant transformation, with a marked shift from Kharif rice to Rabi and summer maize in states such as Bihar, West Bengal, and others, driven by economic incentives, the Ethanol Blending Program, and climate variability. Maize's rising demand in poultry feed, ethanol production, and starch industries, alongside its superior water-use efficiency and resilience to climate stressors, underpins this transition. However, the declining rice acreage threatens food security, given rice's critical role in the Public Distribution System. This market-driven shift, unsupported by Minimum Support Price, necessitates strategic policy interventions to balance resource efficiency with national food security imperatives.

KEYWORDS: agricultural transition, Kharif rice, summer maize, Ethanol Blending Program, food security, climate resilience

The Indian agricultural sector, which supports the livelihood of about 50% of the population, is undergoing a major transition in its cultivation of foodgrains. Being the staple food for large sections of its society, Wheat and Rice account for the majority of the foodgrain production in India with over 75% of the total share (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, 2023). However, in states like Bihar, West Bengal, Jharkhand, and parts of Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka, farmers are steadily moving away from the conventional Kharif rice. This declining trend of rice across several traditionally monsoon-rice states is now substituted by a marked increase in Rabi and summer maize, and in some cases, wheat. What seems surprising is driven primarily by economic incentives, government policy programs such as the Ethanol Blending Program (EBP), water and energy use efficiency, maize's integration into feed and biofuel value chains and climate variability (Observer Research Foundation, 2023).

The sudden increase in maize and the development of its value chain is heavily supported by private players. Maize, which is a primary fodder crop, has found a growing versatile industrial market. High demand for maize is primarily due to poultry feed companies, ethanol manufacturers as well as starch and food processing companies. Furthermore, for the purpose of cutting down India's crude oil imports, the Government of India has launched its Ethanol Blending Program (EBP) wherein petrol blended with ethanol is promoted. New grain-based distilleries in the states of **Bihar, Maharashtra, MP, and Telangana are directly linked to an increase in the production of maize.** (NITI Aayog & Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas. (2021). *Roadmap for*

Ethanol Blending in India 2020–2025.) But, most of this demand is by private players and there is no Minimum Support Price (MSP) or a government procurement system for maize which makes its cultivation risky and uncertain for farmers. Therefore, maize has become a 'market-led' crop as opposed to rice being 'policy-led'.

Although this diversification in yield can help enhance efficiency of natural resources, it is tempered by growing concerns over food security of India and decline of crop varieties that are well-aligned with the Indian monsoons—Kharif rice (Observer Research Foundation, 2023).

MoA data from 2018–2023 shows a notable fall in the area under Kharif rice while the non-existent summer maize (Zaid maize) has surged incrementally in both Bihar and West Bengal (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, 2023). Research suggests that Boro rice growth has been stagnating in Bihar while there has been a consistent increase in both summer and Rabi maize in the state with a CAGR of 2.93% (Kumar & Kumar, 2024). Studies reveal that this shift can be attributed to the improved water-use efficiency in maize, its shorter crop duration, and its growing value chain along with higher prices (Observer Research Foundation, 2023). Maize redeems itself as a more resilient alternative in the increasingly flood-prone low-lying districts in the eastern part of the country, making Kharif rice an unsuitable alternative (Observer Research Foundation, 2023).

In West Bengal, data reveals that even though rainfall has been largely supportive of monsoon-aligned rice, the state continues to record a steadily falling rice acreage (Observer Research Foundation, 2023). As rice continues to form the backbone of the Indian Public Distribution System (PDS),

this growing shift towards summer maize and Rabi wheat poses as a potential concern for the policymakers. The replacement of Kharif rice by maize, especially in high rainfall areas, is likely an indication towards underutilisation of the monsoon potential. Additionally, the growing reliance of maize for ethanol production which has led to spikes in summer and Rabi maize is also turning out to be resource intensive for farmers in the region (Kumar & Kumar, 2024). The agricultural transitions caused by climate change has further made Kharif rice more unsuitable and unsustainable in various eastern and central states of India. The erratic monsoon and increased likelihood of floods coupled with growing heat stress during flowering and grain filling stages has rendered rice as risky choice for farmers. (Indian Council of Agricultural Research, 2022). In eastern districts like Gaya (Bihar) and Murshidabad (West Bengal), the average maximum temperatures that have risen by over 1.2°C in the past 20 years, cause severe impacts. This surge has tremendously affected yields for rice in the region. On the contrary, short duration hybrids of maize make it more climate resilient than other foodgrains and are a pragmatic alternative for risk management and assured yield. This growing preference for maize does not come without its own set of risks. Maize has greater nutritional needs and is known to be quite vulnerable to pest cycles. Additionally, maize is majorly a fodder crop and substituting it for rice does raise more macroeconomic concerns like greater food inflation. This pattern is not isolated to the eastern states; farmers in Jammu & Kashmir, Punjab and some districts of Karnataka are increasingly experimenting with maize outside of its conventional cropping seasons. These discrepancies from traditional patterns are enabled by borewell irrigation which again, puts pressure on the declining water table (Observer Research Foundation, 2023). The evolving crop patterns across India underscore the need for policymakers to practice caution while pushing for fodder

and biofuel crops like maize. While the rise of maize, particularly in summer and Rabi, allows farmers to make better returns while ensuring efficient use of resources, it also raises concerns regarding food security. The contraction of Kharif rice in monsoon-fed regions is suggestive of a possible mismatch between natural resource availability and agricultural planning. Therefore, strengthening the maize production must be integrated with careful regulation to ensure it complements rather than compromises food security goals (Observer Research Foundation, 2023; Kumar & Kumar, 2024).

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